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**USING THE INDIVIDUAL APPROACH METHOD IN ORGANIZING
INDIVIDUAL LESSONS IN CHILDREN'S MUSIC AND ART SCHOOLS**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the theoretical foundations and practical possibilities of using the individual approach method in the process of individual lessons in children's music and art schools. An individual approach involves adapting the educational process taking into account the student's personal abilities, psychological characteristics, level of knowledge and skills. The article highlights ways to identify students' creative potential, motivate them, direct them to independent work, and develop their performing skills through this method in individual lessons. It is also emphasized that such didactic and pedagogical approaches as the formation of interactive communication between the teacher and the student, the selection of repertoire based on an individual approach, and the management of the intensity of training are of great importance. At the end of the study, the positive impact of an individual approach on the effectiveness of children's music education is substantiated.

Keywords: individual approach, individual lesson, music education, children's art school, performance, repertoire selection, motivation, student-teacher dialogue.

Introduction.

The modern educational process should be organized taking into account the individual potential, interests and personal uniqueness of each student. This approach is especially important in the field of music and art. Because in the process of artistic and aesthetic education, each student's abilities, level of musical hearing, creative thinking and emotional sensitivity are different. Individual lessons held in children's music and art schools serve as the most convenient pedagogical space for identifying and developing these individual characteristics.

Today, the priority of concepts such as "humanism" and "personalized education" in education increases the need for the method of an individual approach. In individual music lessons, this method can be used to develop educational strategies tailored to the student's development pace, psychological state, learning difficulties, and areas of interest. This, on the one hand, increases the effectiveness of the lesson, and on the other hand, contributes to the child's creative growth, strengthening self-confidence, and in-depth mastery of musical means of expression. This article discusses the necessity, content, and effectiveness of using the individual approach method in the process of individual lessons in children's music and art schools from a scientific and pedagogical point of view. Along with the theoretical foundations of this approach, practical methodological aspects are also analyzed and ways of applying it to the lesson process are considered.

Individual lessons are the main form of the individual learning process that occurs between the student and the teacher. Especially in children's music and art schools, through this type of lessons, the student's musical abilities are identified, developed, and brought to perfection. The use of the individual approach method in individual lessons allows the teacher to choose an approach that suits the needs of each student.

The practical application of this method ensures that communication takes place in a trusting, friendly environment, allows the student to understand himself, think independently, and freely express his feelings. Each child is unique with his inner world, abilities, and musical taste. Therefore, the content of the lesson, the system of exercises, and the repertoire are also selected depending on the age characteristics, level of development, psychological state, and motivational needs of the student.

For example, when working with students at the initial stage, it is advisable to teach through game-style approaches, figurative representations, and simple types of musical expression. When the student feels his success, tries to independently express small musical ideas, he sees himself as a creator, and this strengthens his love for music.

Another important aspect of the individual approach is the choice of a flexible and dynamic approach to lesson planning, rather than rigid schemes. Each lesson is adapted to the current state of the student: if the child is emotionally exhausted, the lesson is conducted in a gentle tone, if he is active and curious, complex performance tasks are given.

In this process, the teacher's pedagogical skills, psychological sensitivity and creative approach are of great importance. In this way, individual lessons become an important pedagogical environment that serves the comprehensive development of the student's personality. The goal is to form the student as a creative, independent thinker, with musical imagination.

Literature review:

The scientific and theoretical foundations of the method of individual approach in children's music education are widely covered in many foreign and domestic pedagogical literature. Among the Uzbek pedagogical scientists G.G. Joraev, N.K. Karimova, O.M. The scientific research of the Tashkulovs deeply covers the issues of person-centered education, differential approach and musical aesthetic education. In particular, the works of G.G. Juraev on the individual approach in music education describe the pedagogical mechanisms for identifying and developing the student's personal abilities.

In foreign literature, H. Gardner's "theory of multiple intelligences" emphasizes the recognition of musical abilities as an independent intellect, the need to take into account the fact that each child has his own musical thinking in lessons. Also, such prominent figures of music pedagogy as K. Orff, Z. Kodaly and E. Gordon proposed the practical application of an individual approach in their methods.

Especially E. Gordon's theory of "audition" (inner hearing) is relevant in the development of individual characteristics of children's musical perception.

Local practical experience shows the effectiveness of an individual approach by adapting musical tasks in individual lessons, paying attention to the emotional state of the student, and relying on personal taste and abilities when choosing a repertoire. Thus, an analysis of scientific literature shows that the theoretical and practical foundations of the individual approach method have been thoroughly developed, and especially in aesthetic activities such as music education, this approach serves to fully reveal the creative potential of the student. Adapting this approach to individual lessons in children's art schools significantly increases the quality of education.

Discussion.

The individual approach method is one of the most important pedagogical methods for effectively organizing individual lessons. This approach allows for a deep study of the personal capabilities of each student, taking into account their interests and psychological state, and adapting the educational process. In particular, the use of this method in music and art education creates a wide opportunity to reveal the child's emotional sensitivity, creative thinking, and performing abilities.

Individual lessons are based on personal communication, and in this type of lesson a trusting, friendly atmosphere is formed between the teacher and the student. In such conditions, the teacher teaches each child on the basis of a separate individual approach: someone has a strong sensitivity to sound, while another has a sense of rhythm or creative expression. Therefore, it is necessary to adapt the content and form of classes for each student. This requires great pedagogical skills, psychological sensitivity and a creative approach from the teacher. Also, through an individual approach, it is possible to ensure the student's active participation in the lesson, encourage independent thinking, and develop skills for working on themselves. The student's musical taste, technical capabilities and personal interests are also taken into account when choosing a repertoire. This makes the lesson a truly interesting and inspiring process for the student.

But this process also poses certain problems. First, creating an individual program for each student and personalizing lessons takes a lot of time and effort. Secondly, not all teachers may be sufficiently prepared to work in this way. Therefore, it is important to organize special trainings and seminars in the system of art schools to improve the skills of teachers and in-depth mastery of the individual approach methodology. In general, the use of the individual approach method in individual lessons serves not only to deeply master musical knowledge and skills, but also to enhance the student's personal development, strengthen self-confidence, and increase the desire for independent creativity. This method allows building the musical education process on the principles of humanity, creativity, and individual orientation.

Conclusion.

Individual lessons in children's music and art schools are not only a place for teaching musical knowledge and skills, but also an important pedagogical process that allows you to find a way to the heart of each child, discover his inner world, understand his personal needs and develop his individuality. The use of the individual approach method in this process makes the relationship between the teacher and the student human, sincere and creative.

By using the individual approach method, lessons are not the same, but are tailored to each student, interesting and effective. Each child is brought up in an environment where he can reveal his strengths, which further strengthens his love for music and stimulates his creative thinking. This approach serves to organize education taking into account the child's personal needs, emotional state, psychological characteristics and pace of development.

For the effective use of the individual approach method in individual lessons, the teacher's high pedagogical culture, musical knowledge, as well as the ability to understand and feel the child are also important. Also, constant analysis of the lesson process, monitoring the development dynamics of each student, and choosing appropriate methodological tools are factors that determine the success of this approach.

In conclusion, an individual approach to music and art education is an important requirement of modern education, which serves to develop the student not only as a learner, but also as a creative person. Teachers who have deeply mastered this method awaken a love of art in the hearts of children, educate them as independent creative and aesthetic thinkers in the future.

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